

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to provide solutions for the methodological issues with the way English is taught in high school. The most successful of them in the context of the problem of a choice of technologies and methods of teaching English in a modern higher education institution are proven in this article by examination and research of theoretical and methodical elements of novel technologies of training.

Searching for innovative approaches, strategies, and technological advancements that will support the efficient instruction of students, especially foreign languages, is mandated by the modernization of higher professional education. The continual information content of the curriculum and the activation of the learning pace via the use of contemporary information technology are characteristics of modern education that should be observed in order to attain great educational achievements. The writers of contemporary scientific and methodological literature are increasingly focusing on the rationale behind the novel learning technologies' great educational potential and their efficacy in the high school English teaching system.

Many researchers, who have provided evidence of the effective use of new technologies in the training of future experts, such as foreign language instructors, have emphasized the need to increase the proportion of interactive learning and the predominance of novel pedagogical technologies over conventional ones. However, we believe it is important to acknowledge the perspective of those scholars who, seeing that traditional reproductive forms and teaching methods are insufficient at this point in the development of the educational system and foreign language teaching techniques, favor an integrative approach that combines the use of various cutting-edge pedagogical technologies with the preservation of objectively sound traditional educational techniques. This approach impresses us with the opportunity to preserve the academic character and universality of higher education and to form the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for a modern teacher through the use of new teaching technologies. Having outlined his methodological position regarding traditional and innovative methods and learning technologies, in this article it is advisable to

analyze the theoretical aspects of innovative learning technologies and turn to a direct consideration of the most effective technologies that can be used in higher education in the system of teaching English language.

Presentation of the article's main points. There is a trend in higher professional education to devote more hours for students to work independently and less hours for classroom instruction at this point in its growth. In this sense, we can say that the function of the teacher in the educational process is changing in the modern day. The teacher was once thought of as the primary knowledge source, but in modern times, his function may be more accurately described as that of an expert, adviser, and organizer of the future specialists' educational and self-educational efforts. Such transformations became possible due to the emergence and widespread introduction of innovative and more effective technologies, forms and means of education into the educational process of higher education, which make it possible to optimize the process of professional training of future specialists as part of their studies at the university. The high productivity and efficiency of innovative technologies in the context of training future specialists is substantiated by their multi functionality. Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies perform the following functions in the educational process:

1. formative;
2. motivating;
3. systematizing;
4. controlling.

Innovative technologies and teaching methods help achieve the following goals:

- a. accessibility perception of educational material;
- b. systematization of knowledge;
- c. development of creative abilities of students;
- d. self-education;
- e. removing the psychological barrier (fear of communicating, making a mistake); understanding educational material, analysis of learned material [4].

To effective innovative pedagogical technologies that can be applied in the system teaching English in higher education with a high level of performance relative to achievement of educational results, researchers most often refer to interactive distance learning technologies (Skype, Viber, WhatsApp, e-mail, Internet chat, etc.), computer learning tools (electronic manuals, textbooks, sources of virtual libraries, educational portals, etc.), multimedia learning resources, training and testing and other latest information technologies[1].

Tangible progress in terms of the effectiveness of English language teaching both in humanitarian and technical universities, according to researchers, was achieved through a wide use of electronic teaching aids in the educational process of the higher school. These tools are used both in the classroom and extracurricular (distance) learning [4]. Didactic Potential of Electronic Learning Tools in English Classes lies in the fact that their use in the educational process contributes to:

- better assimilation of knowledge by students;

- the formation and development of different types of skills and abilities (listening skills based on adapted and authentic sound texts, the ability to reproduce monologue and dialogic speech, the ability and skills of translation and abstracting of texts, the ability and skills of reading with the direct use of materials from the Internet and local networks;
- increasing the informative richness and visibility of the lesson;
- expansion of active and passive dictionaries of students, familiarization with the vocabulary of modern English, which reproduces the culture of a particular country, its political and social device;
- formation of creativity, development of creative activity of future specialists;
- the formation of motivation for the cognitive activity of students, the need to use foreign language in interactive communication;
- strengthening the motivation of independent work of students;
- increasing the level of individualization and differentiation of students' activities;
- the ability to choose the pace and volume of educational material, the level of its complexity, to implement control with feedback and diagnostics, to increase the level of its objectivity [3].

At the present stage, the leading information technology, the means of which are used in almost all spheres of human activity, is the Internet. Internet resources provide not only the availability of a number of additional means of implementing interpersonal and international communication, but also provide new opportunities in the field of education [5]. Within the framework of this technology, the education system uses information sites and portals, educational programs on electronic media, the ability to obtain information, implement consulting and control knowledge remotely via e-mail, online conferences and video classes. The advantages of the Internet as an innovative learning tool stem from the fact that it provides a limitless source of information, which allows both the teacher and students to save time to search for the necessary material (theoretical, textual, sound, visual information, etc.); provides great opportunities for creativity in terms of developing didactic material, forms and types of work, individual and group tasks, projects; improves efficiency teaching a foreign language due to the possibility of total immersion in the language material and increasing the motivation of students to learn [8]. Today, in the system of teaching and learning foreign languages, increasing popularity due to Interactive online learning is gaining its effectiveness. The effectiveness of this technology due to a number of advantages, among which researchers highlight accessibility, flexibility, lack of stress for students, high quality of education, the possibility of personal consultations, the choice of time and place for learning, saving time, improving computer skills in the process of learning a foreign language [6]. In the system of teaching and learning English, new horizons are opening up today for the first time. turn multimedia learning tools through a combination of images, sound, graphics, animation. Researchers L.S. Dzhumanova, B.M. Toimbaeva, M.K. Tulegenov in this vein emphasize: "thanks to the optimal combination of the capabilities of a number of technical teaching aids (language laboratory, video films, television, radio, newspapers, magazines, books, bibliographic directories, phone) and having additional features (interactivity, graphic opportunities, etc.), multimedia provides almost limitless opportunities for learning and self-learning" [2, p. 523].

The use of innovative learning tools brings change and organizational structure educational process: the requirements for the methods and forms of organization of teaching foreign languages - active and interactive individual and group forms of work with educational material become leading. In the context of building classes based on the use of innovative technologies and teaching aids, the type of activity and the nature of the relationship between the teacher and students are changing. The role of the student turns into an active cognitive position, while the teacher, in turn, acts as a coordinator, consultant, partner. Summarizing the foregoing, we conclude that, along with the indicated advantages analyzed learning technologies, it is not worth leveling the importance of academic forms of obtaining knowledge and formation of students' competencies. The use of modern technologies in the classroom English should not be an end in itself. These technologies should be taken into account the importance of effective didactic and technical teaching aids.

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